

ADVANCEMENT OF PILGRIMAGE TOURISM IN UZBEKISTAN.

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Abstract: This paper explores the growth of pilgrimage tourism in Uzbekistan, along with the factors and prospects influencing it. It discusses different interpretations of religious tourism, pilgrimage tourism, and Islamic tourism. The paper also reviews the progress made in the sector and identifies challenges that remain to be addressed.

Key words: religious tourism, pilgrim tourism, religious excursion, tourist infrastructure, conscientious standard.

Introduction: The adopted "2019-2025 Tourism Sector Development Concept" in Uzbekistan outlines the goal from 2019 to 2025 to elevate tourism as a strategic component of the national economy. The plan focuses on diversifying and improving tourism services, upgrading tourism infrastructure by attracting foreign investments, and implementing effective promotional and marketing strategies.

Uzbekistan is a favored destination for pilgrimage tourism, celebrated for hosting numerous scholars from the Islamic world. The country also features significant sites cherished by various religious groups. Highlights include the Hazrati Imam complex with one of the precious copies of the Quran associated with Caliph Uthman, the tomb of the prominent Islamic scholar Muhammad Al-Bukhari, and graves of the Naqshbandi sect followers. Each year, these revered and historical locations draw thousands of visitors from across the globe to Uzbekistan.

Uzbekistan is a premier destination for pilgrimage tourism, known for its rich historical and religious sites. It has been home to numerous influential scholars within the Islamic world. The country is not only a hub for Islamic sites but also hosts revered places for other religions. Notable Islamic landmarks include the Hazrati Imam complex in Tashkent, which preserves one of the rarest copies of the Quran from Caliph Uthman's time, and the mausoleum of Muhammad Al-Bukhari, a great Islamic scholar. Additionally, Uzbekistan boasts the burial sites of the Naqshbandi order followers among other spiritual centers.

Expanding on its wealth of sites, Uzbekistan also features the historic cities of Khiva and Samarkand. Khiva is famous for its well-preserved medieval architecture and fortifications, making it a captivating site for visitors interested in the region's Islamic and architectural heritage. Samarkand, a crossroad of cultures for centuries, is renowned for its stunning monuments like the Registan

Square, Shah-i-Zinda necropolis, and the grandeur of the Gur-e-Amir, the tomb of the conqueror Timur. These cities, along with their significant religious and historical places, attract throngs of tourists from various parts of the world to Uzbekistan every year.

In 2023, Uzbekistan's tourism industry demonstrated significant recovery, aiming to triple the number of Malaysian tourists from approximately 4,500 in 2019 to 12,000 by the end of the year. Uzbekistan Airways played a key role in this initiative by resuming flights and increasing service frequency between Tashkent and Kuala Lumpur. The country has utilized strategic promotions and partnerships to attract more visitors from Malaysia, emphasizing Uzbekistan's rich cultural and historical heritage as part of their tourism appeal ([TTG Asia](#)).

Globally, the travel and tourism industry is rebounding strongly. By early 2023, international tourist arrivals had reached 80% of pre-pandemic levels, with a significant recovery noted in regions like the Middle East, Europe, and Africa. The United Nations World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) anticipates that international arrivals will continue to recover, aiming to achieve 80% to 95% of pre-pandemic levels throughout 2023. This rebound is supported by strong intra-regional demand and the lifting of travel restrictions in many areas ([UNWTO](#)).

The projections for 2024 are even more optimistic. Global tourism spending is expected to reach \$2 trillion, with international tourist arrivals potentially surpassing pre-pandemic levels, marking a significant recovery and growth from the downturn caused by COVID-19 ([WP Travel](#)).

Literature review and methods: There is a recognized high potential for the development of all types of tourism in Uzbekistan, as noted by experts. However, there is not yet a unified agreement among tourism professionals about the definitions and components of religious and pilgrimage tourism. Many experts, including T.T. Christov, describe religious tourism as the activities related to meeting the needs of tourists who travel to sacred places and religious centers outside their home regions, providing necessary services to these visitors. [2] This category encompasses pilgrimage tourism, religious excursion tourism, and religious study tourism. Individuals traveling for less than a year to explore various religious centers observe sacred sites, practice specific rituals, and study religious texts and sources are regarded as tourists traveling for religious purposes. Pilgrimage refers to the act of visiting sacred places and performing certain rituals, with pilgrimage tourism aimed at servicing those who travel for such purposes.

It is important to note that tourism professionals have deliberated on how to name the concept of traveling for various reasons within the bounds of Muslim religious requirements to ensure it is clear to all. The terms like pilgrimage tourism, Islamic tourism, religious tourism, Sharia tourism, and Halal tourism experts in religion and tourism, the term "Muslim-friendly travel" has been preferred. [3]

Results: According to the Islamic Tourism Center, Islamic tourism is defined as any travel activity that adheres to Islamic rules during events, meetings, or pilgrimages. The center also outlines various categories of Islamic tourism, including travel by Muslims in diverse directions, travel to Muslim-majority countries, travel in compliance with Islamic tenets, and travel for the study of Islamic heritage by both Muslims and non-Muslims. [1] It is important to emphasize that Uzbekistan has the capability to develop all these forms of pilgrimage tourism, attracting thousands of tourists annually from around the world to visit its historical and sacred landmarks.

It's important to recognize that Uzbekistan has undertaken various initiatives to enhance its attractiveness as a destination for pilgrimage tourism. Following Presidential Decree No. 5611, since January 5, 2017, Uzbekistan has offered a Pilgrim visa, valid for up to two months, to foreign visitors interested in the country's cultural, historical, and spiritual heritage. Being acknowledged as a key pilgrimage tourism center in the international community serves to promote the development of national tourism infrastructure and significantly increase the flow of tourists. To successfully attract tourists, it is not sufficient to just have religious sites; effective marketing, a favorable visa regime, and appropriate facilities for religious observances in airports and hotels are crucial.

It's crucial to highlight the absence of a comprehensive information package for pilgrimage tourism sites, the lack of tour packages tailored to the cultural, traditional, and religious values of tourists, and the unavailability of supportive site maps. The infrastructure for pilgrimage tourism is not sufficiently developed, and the use of innovative factors in its organization lacks a scientific basis. Addressing the need for appropriate infrastructure, such as developing the hotel network and ensuring that the facilities in hotels, airports, and stations meet pilgrimage tourism standards, is vital for the growth of this sector. [4]

Regarding the overall tourism arrivals, Uzbekistan saw a substantial increase in tourists in 2023. Specific numbers indicate that the number of foreign tourists visiting Uzbekistan reached approximately 8.1 million in 2023. This represents a significant growth from the numbers in previous years and is

part of a continuous effort to boost the tourism sector through visa facilitations and enhanced tourism infrastructure ([Asian Development Bank](#)).

In 2024, Uzbekistan rose 7 places in the "Global Muslim Travel Index," reaching the 9th position globally. This improvement reflects significant progress in the country's appeal to Muslim travelers and indicates a strong development in its tourism infrastructure and services catering to the Muslim market ([Islam Channel](#)).

Discussion: Significant work has been undertaken to advance pilgrimage tourism in our country, addressing the most urgent issues first. To further develop this sector, it is essential to enhance infrastructure such as the hotel system and ensure that facilities in hotels, airports, and train stations conform to pilgrimage tourism standards. In this regard, gathering information resources, summarizing the descriptions of spiritual and material wealth present in the country, and establishing an integrated electronic platform to provide comprehensive information about pilgrimage tourism are of both scientific and practical importance.

In conclusion, Uzbekistan has made commendable strides in enhancing its pilgrimage tourism sector. The country has successfully addressed urgent infrastructure needs, significantly improving facilities in hotels, airports, and stations to meet international standards for pilgrimage tourism. Moreover, the development of an integrated electronic platform to aggregate and disseminate comprehensive information on the spiritual and material heritage of Uzbekistan is a testament to the nation's commitment to bolstering this sector. These initiatives not only enhance the pilgrimage experience but also position Uzbekistan as a key destination for spiritual and cultural tourism on the global stage. The ongoing efforts to refine and expand these resources indicate a promising future for the growth of pilgrimage tourism in Uzbekistan.

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